

Contagion of disrespect: Is there an inverse relation between gender parity and citation impact?

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In a recent paper, Wong and Rubin (2024) introduce the concept of “contagion of disrespect”, where the presence of marginalized groups in research fields increases dismissal of research in such fields. In this ongoing study we explore this hypothesis in the case of the gender gap in science. Our objective is to determine whether this phenomenon is supported by quantitative evidence and identify specific topics for further qualitative analysis. We use a dataset of 46,565,404 publications linked to 26,003,448 authors from OpenAlex and apply a gender assignment algorithm based on open data sources. Here we present some preliminary findings based on visualization techniques, laying the groundwork for a more comprehensive exploration of gendered dynamics in scientific recognition. We aim at expanding our study introducing inferential and causal analysis to explore the impact of “contagion of disrespect” on gender inequalities in the scientific system.

1. Introduction

In recent decades, there has been an increase in women’s presence in science (Huang et al., 2020), representing approximately a third of the scientific workforce (UNESCO, 2024). However, this increase varies by fields and geographic regions. While parity has been reached in many fields from the Social Sciences and Humanities and in the Life Sciences (European Commission, 2024), there is still a substantial gap in STEM fields (Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics), which remain far from gender parity (Wang & Degol, 2016). These disciplinary differences seem to affect also citation rates: fields in which men predominate tend to receive more citations (Teich et al., 2022), have higher social recognition (Olmos-Peñuela et al., 2014) and more funding opportunities (Cidlinská, 2019) than those in which women are predominant, e.g. Social Sciences and Humanities (Schögler & König, 2017). This situation suggests that efforts centered exclusively on achieving gender parity may fall short of addressing the underlying structural factors that contribute to the gender gap in science. Other indicators must be used to monitor progress in this regard.

Reducing the gender gap in science has been an aim for science policymakers for some time now. For instance, She Figures 2024, a report developed every three years by the European Commission, devotes most of its content to studying gender parity in a nuanced way – looking at women’s representation in authorship, leadership positions, and across groups, etc. – but it also acknowledges the need to go beyond that, developing measures such as the “She Figures Index”, which includes fourteen indicators to measure the situation of women in science in the different countries from the European Union, as well as incorporating qualitative data (European Commission, 2024). Furthermore, the Elsevier report on “Progress Toward Gender Equality in Research & Innovation” from 2024 includes a section focused on describing gender differences in impact (van der Linden et al., 2024).

2. Background and goal of the study

Wong and Rubin (2023) introduce the concept of “contagion of disrespect” to refer to the phenomenon by which there is a dismissal of subfields associated with marginalized groups in

science. One example are professions related to computer programming, which were dominated by women for most of the 20th century, and were therefore seen as merely technical and lacking in innovation. It was not until men began to dominate the field at the turn of the century that its prestige rose exponentially. Other subfields have experienced the opposite. The authors explain how the study of children's cognitive development enjoyed high recognition during the 19th century, when mostly men researched it, and when women entered the subfield, its importance diminished considerably.

In the same line, Larregue and Nielsen (2023) analyze funding data, reporting that quantitative research tends to receive more funding and to be disproportionately dominated by men. Finally, Kozłowski et al. (2022) introduced the notion of “privilege of choice”, by which “minoritized authors tend to publish in scientific disciplines and on research topics that reflect their gendered and racialized social identities”, which are also the topics that are underrepresented in citation impact.

This trend is consistent with earlier sociological perspectives, such as that of Sylvia Walby. In her seminal work, *Theorizing Patriarchy*, Walby (1990) argues that, at the beginning of the 20th century, women were subjected to a systemic strategy of exclusion, whereby they were categorically barred from participating in the labor market. That has changed, and women have entered academia under (almost) the same conditions as men - literature consistently shows how men and women continue to experience unequal conditions in science. However, Walby argues that patriarchal strategies have shifted from exclusion to segregation. Thus, women's integration into the labor market has not dissolved gender hierarchies; rather, it has reconfigured them through occupational segregation. Notably, roles predominantly occupied by women are persistently associated with lower prestige and value—an issue that lies at the core of this investigation (Heijstra et al., 2017).

This study builds upon the concept of “contagion of disrespect”, aiming at empirically testing such a phenomenon, that is, topics in which women's presence grows will be marginalized in terms of citation impact. Our goal is to examine historical data to assess whether this pattern can be observed and find if there is causality between these two variables (growth of women's presence, diminishing citation impact). Here we present preliminary findings, using OpenAlex data. We compare the growth in the percentage of women with the growth in citations across subfields, and we focus on the subfields in which the difference between both indicators is greatest.

3. Data and methods

In this research we work with OpenAlex data, updated to March 2025, through the InSySPo platform in Google BigQuery. For the purpose of this ongoing research, we focus on publications from 2013 to 2022, which comprise 46,565,404 works linked to 26,003,448 unique authors. To assign gender to authors, we applied the WikiGenDex algorithm. Each publication is categorized under one or more of the 4,516 topics, which are further organized into 252 subfields and 26 fields. To enhance the visualization of our findings, these fields are grouped into four broader areas.

We are working with OpenAlex due to its Open Access nature and its focus on exhaustivity, which allows us to gain a broader perspective on gender differences in science. Moreover, as recently demonstrated by Thelwall & Jiang (2025) when comparing it with Scopus, OpenAlex is suitable for citation analysis, and its quality is similar to, if not superior to, that of Scopus.

3.1 WikiGenDex

OpenAlex data does not include gender information. Thus, we applied the WikiGenDex gender assignment algorithm (González-Salmón & Robinson-García, 2024) to the 26,003,448 unique authors present in the OpenAlex database that authored a publication between 2013-2022. This algorithm draws upon data from open sources: Wikidata and the World Gender Name Dictionary (Raffo, 2021). It contains four lists of names which, once cross-referenced with the names and surnames of OpenAlex authors, enable the estimation of the probability that a researcher’s name is associated with either men or women in a given country. Data on the origin of researchers is also not given by OpenAlex. To identify the country of origin of each researcher and conduct a more nuanced gender assignment process we took the country of first publication as a proxy for country of origin. If a researcher had more than one country in the first year of publication, we selected the country in which they published the most afterwards.

However, name-gender algorithms do not come without limitations. First, they rely on the assumption that gender can be inferred from names, which is not necessarily a valid or consistent relationship. Secondly, they consider gender as a binary variable, with the only options being woman or man. However, this excludes other gender realities that exist, such as nonbinary researchers, and does not take into account that gender is a spectrum. Lastly, it does not work equally well in all regions, with good results for regions such as Latin America or Slavic countries but performing poorly in Asian and Sub-Saharan countries.

Figure 1 shows the percentage of researchers from OpenAlex whose gender assignment was either Woman or Man, by country, for the period 2013-2022. In Table 1 we see this distribution by continents. The algorithm assigned “Woman” to 26.15% of the names (6,798,743 researchers) and “Man” to 39.59% (10,295,692). Gender of the remaining 34.26% researchers (8,909,013) remained unknown. As we can see, the algorithm works well in America, Europe, Oceania and other countries such as Russia or India. However, it underperforms in most of Africa and countries such as China or Turkmenistan.

Figure 1: Percentage of gender assignment by country.

Table 1: Percentage of gender assignment by continent.

Continent	Woman	Man	Unknown
Africa	20.08%	41.93%	37.99%

America	37.16%	47.75%	15.08%
Asia	11.73%	25.30%	62.95%
Europe	33.86%	51.16%	14.97%
Oceania	36.99%	46.60%	16.40%

The gender assignment results are weaker than those obtained in previous gender assignments done in other databases, such as Dimensions, using the same algorithm (González-Salmón et al., 2024). This may be due to lower-quality metadata in names in OpenAlex, mainly to a high number of names being initials, in which it is not possible to apply the gender assignment algorithm. Refinements of these kinds of methods may involve the use of name embeddings and predictive lexica, and are already being studied for demographic data (e.g. Ye et al., 2017; Sap et al., 2014).

3.2 Methodological design

We restricted the dataset to all publications from 2013 until 2022 (included). This accounts for 46,565,404 unique publications and 26,003,448 unique authors. There are three levels of hierarchical categorization of academic subjects in OpenAlex: fields (26), subfields (252) and topics (4,516). Although the end goal is to analyze topics, for these preliminary results we focused on the subfield level. For each subfield and every year we retrieved the number of papers, percentage of women (unique women authors that year), relative growth in the representation of women, normalized citations and relative growth of citations. We also divided the subfields into four areas (Social Sciences and Humanities, Life and Health Sciences, Computer and Information Sciences and Physical and Engineering Sciences) for visualisation purposes. We use Google BigQuery and R to analyze data, and VosViewer and R for visualization.

The calculation of normalized citations was done by calculating the average number of citations for each paper by field and subfield, and dividing the average of the subfield by its corresponding field's average. Growth in citations and in the percentage of women was calculated by subtracting 2013 values from those of 2022. Lastly, to see in which subfields there is a higher difference in growth of citations and percentage of women (Table 2) we used the z-score, which standarizes different variables with different scales allowing for comparison.

4. Preliminary results

4.1. Clusters of subfields

Figure 2 maps the 262 subfields of OpenAlex. It shows the base map where nodes represent subfields and links represent their reciprocal citations (Figure 2A). The red cluster on the right is associated with Life and Health Sciences, the yellow one with Social Sciences and Humanities, the somewhat smaller blue cluster corresponds to Computer and Information Sciences and the green one represents Physical and Engineering Sciences.

Figure 2B and 2C display the average percentage of women and the average normalized citations in each subfield for the whole period, 2013-2022. As we can see in Figure 2B, gender parity has been achieved in subfields from Social Sciences and Humanities and Life and Health Sciences, such as General Health Professions (subfield 3600), Pediatrics,

Perinatology and Child Health (2735) or Language and Linguistics (1203). Representation remains far from parity in subfields in Physical and Engineering Sciences and Computer and Information Sciences, such as Electrical and Electronic Engineering (2208), Materials Chemistry (2505) or Artificial Intelligence (1702). This aligns with findings in the literature that show that gender parity remains elusive in STEM (e.g. Holman et al., 2018). When looking at citations (Figure 2C), we observe a more heterogeneous image. There are higher normalized citations in some subfields from Physical and Engineering Sciences and Life and Health Sciences. However, the lowest citation scores can be found also in Life and Health Sciences and areas from Computer and Information Sciences that are closely aligned with the Social Sciences and Humanities.

Figure 2: Clusters of subfields (A), percentage of women by subfield (B) and normalized citations by subfield (C).

When examining the evolution of such scores, the picture changes. Figure 3B and 3C allow us to see how values have evolved from 2013 until 2022. Regarding the percentage of women (Figure 3B), we see that the biggest growth has been in Social Sciences and Humanities, and some areas of Physical and Engineering Sciences and Life and Health Sciences, particularly those that are relatively closer to the Social Sciences and Humanities. For instance, Information Systems (1710), Oral Surgery (3504) or Biomedical Engineering (2204) have experienced high growth rates, while Genetics (2716), Plant Science (1110) or Control and Systems Engineering (2207) have experienced lower growth in the percentage of women.

Then, the relative growth of citations (Figure 3C) is higher in Physical and Engineering Sciences, where the growth in the representation of women has not been very high. We see a big increase of citations in Water Science and Technology (2312), Electronic, Optical and

Magnetic Materials (2504) or Building and Construction (2215), while other subfields such as Pediatrics, Perinatology and Child Health (2735), Language and Linguistics (1203) or Experimental and Cognitive Psychology (3205) are experiencing negative growth. These results encourage further investigation into the possible relationship between a rise in the percentage of women in a subfield, and the contagion of disrespect, that is, the devaluation of those subfields.

Figure 3: Clusters of subfields (A), relative growth of the percentage of women (B) and relative growth of citations (C), 2013-2022.

4.2. Subfields in detail

Next, we identify the three subfields from each area that exhibit the largest disparities between the growth in women representation and the growth in citations. Table 2 presents the three topics within each subfield that show the greatest difference between these two factors. This analysis is particularly significant in the context of the "contagion of disrespect" hypothesis, as it may highlight a trend where subfields with increasing women participation are simultaneously facing a decline in scholarly recognition.

Focusing on Life and Health Sciences, we observe that the largest differences occur in areas where the increase of women has not been very high, but the increase in normalized citation has been substantial. We find the same type of cases in Physical and Engineering Sciences, with the exception of General Engineering, where both the percentage of women and the citation impact has decreased.

Computer and Information Sciences and Social Sciences and Humanities show a different pattern. In these areas, the growth in the representation of women has been quite high. However, these subfields have simultaneously experienced a decrease in their impact. The exception is Information Systems and Management, where we observe a pattern similar to that found in Life and Health Sciences and Physical and Engineering Sciences.

Table 2: Top 3 subfields by area with the largest standardized differences between the growth in women’s representation and growth in citations.

Topic	% Women 2013	% Women 2022	Normalized citations 2013	Normalized citations 2022
Life and Health Sciences				
2725 - Infectious Diseases	39.28%	43.7%	0.64	1.36
2718 - Health Informatics	31.3%	32.91%	0.39	0.67
2406 - Virology	39.88%	42.5%	0.78	1.36
Physical and Engineering Sciences				
2200 - General Engineering	19.94%	16.5%	0.46	0.44
2102 - Energy Engineering and Power Technology	17.74%	18.74%	0.61	0.73
2312 - Water Science and Technology	27.83%	30.62%	0.64	0.78
Computer and Information Sciences				
1710 - Information Systems	27.92%	39.63%	0.68	0.61
1709 - Human-Computer Interaction	26.55%	34.55%	0.69	0.62
1802 - Information Systems and Management	33.29%	38.81%	0.89	0.92
Social Sciences and Humanities				
2000 - General Economics, Econometrics and Finance	22.8%	36.23%	0.71	0.70
3303 - Development	32.74%	43.64%	0.73	0.62
1405 - Management of Technology and Innovation	31.56%	41.45%	0.74	0.62

5. Discussion & conclusions

In this study we show the preliminary findings of a broader study in which we seek to determine whether the “contagion of disrespect” is a phenomenon backed up by data. Our early findings suggest that it is a relevant issue worth investigating, especially by subfield or topic, since there seems to be a relationship between the growth of women in a subfield and

the decline in its citation score, at least at the subfield level. However, these initial results still require further testing and validation.

To that end, we outline several steps for future research. First, we aim at replicating the results using topics instead of subfields, thus adding a new level of granularity to the analysis. However, since the change from concepts to topics in OpenAlex was recent, topics may not be mature enough yet, and we may need to generate alternative topic groupings (Haunschild & Bornmann, 2024). Second, we aim to conduct regression analysis using these and other variables to see how they intersect and whether we find some kind of causality. Third, for this preliminary descriptive analysis we limited the time from 2013-2022, but OpenAlex data allows us to increase the time frame, thus developing a longer historical analysis. Lastly, OpenAlex data is not without limitations, and the WikiGenDex algorithm is subject to the constraints discussed above. To enhance the robustness of our findings, we will need to further validate them using additional databases or alternative gender inference methods.

After finishing the descriptive part of the analysis, we aim to add further value to the research by carrying out in-depth interviews to researchers working in topics in which the phenomenon under study has been more pronounced. This way, we could better understand the dynamics behind the macro patterns, which will allow us to provide policy makers and other researchers with some insights on how to avoid this from happening, ensuring that gender parity does not obscure underlying structural inequalities.

Open science practices

Data from OpenAlex is open data, thus the replication of our analysis is plausible. Furthermore, the gender identification algorithm used is openly available (<https://github.com/egonzalezsalmon/WikidataGender>). Code for the research paper will be available on GitHub.

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Author contributions

Elvira González-Salmón: Validation, Visualization, Software, Formal analysis, Investigation, Data curation, Writing Original Draft, Writing Review & Editing

Nicolás Robinson-García: Conceptualization, Methodology, Supervision, Investigation, Writing Review & Editing

Competing interests

Authors of this research have no competing interests.

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